

Science of Rahu Kaal

57 Comments / English Blogs / By Deepanshu Giri

We all have heard this term from our elders to not perform anything during the Rahu kaal as every day for 90 minutes there is a Rahu kaal – A time period of 90 minutes where we should not buy new things or start anything new instead, we should focus on spiritual activities.

As working with Panchang for the last several years and observing various patterns on a daily basis, which we also shared in our telegram group, Rahu kaal standing true to its name was always the mystery, but to solve any mystery of the universe, we need to experience it, We need to find ways to measure the subtle changes which are happening around us as this whole universe.

Rahu Kaal is calculated by dividing the time of Sunrise- Sunset into eight different parts, and based on each day, this time period is given; based on local sunrise and sunset time, this time will differ, and it is best to check local panchang for the Rahu Kaalam.

Monday: 7:30 a.m.–9:00 a.m. (2nd part)

Tuesday: 3:00 p.m.–4:30 p.m. (7th part)

Wednesday: 12:00 p.m.–1:30 p.m. (5th part)

Thursday: 1:30 p.m.–3:00 p.m. (6th part)

Friday: 10:30 a.m.–12:00 p.m. (4th part)

Saturday: 9:00 a.m.–10:30 a.m. (3rd part)

Sunday: 4:30 p.m.–6:00 p.m. (8th part)

My question to myself was, Why is this time period given to Rahu as any time allocated to Rahu in the panchang is when there is a void of energy? You are unsure of anything. This is the Zero time period of the universe, such as Ashtami and Amavas tithi in panchang belongs to Rahu, and this is the tithi of indecisiveness, A tithi of a black hole. Still, these tithis are the best remedies for life's chronic problems.

To understand this, we need first to understand why there are only seven days a week, not 5 or 10- as if it would come to me, I would choose to have four days in a week or, like Romans, had eight days in a week, or Egyptians had ten days in their weekly calendar but since Hindu calendar was based on the movement of planets and all rituals are designed around this calendar so the humans can uplift themselves and gather energy from space using the movement of planets, As human DNA corresponds to different planets in different months and energy of planets and this is what our ancient rishis called as Graha Shanti.

This whole world works on a rhythm from human life to the Stock market. This rhythm is superior to any other cycle; as

on Twitter till now, without any technical parameter and against all odds, only on the basis of this cycle, I was able to point out 15 stocks and from the last three years, over ten multi-baggers. Still, we can use the same cycle and use it for the whole universe.

Coming back to the number of days in a week confining to seven, given we have seven planets in this universe and each day is named after them starting from Sunday. Moreover, the 28-day moon cycle is divided into four parts- New Moon- Full Moon- Half Moon – So the Moon will be in Kendra precisely 90 degrees from the New Moon origin after seven days. The day New Moon is rising and after every seven days, the same weekday will be repeated and based on this, you can make predictions.

Such as, any month which has 5 Saturdays will be extremely tough, and oil/steel/machinery prices will rise in this month; a month with five Mondays will bring emotional turmoil but will be suitable for FMCG sectors and Car Sales, but every day when Sunrise- we calculate the tithi based on the distance between Sun and Moon and this Tithi is the emotion and relation between not only Sun and Moon but also between – Atman and Mann.

Atman is someone who is deeply buried inside us but cannot communicate until and unless we go into deep isolation and listen to our own sound- All the Beej Mantras are nothing but the sounds of Atman, and we chant them to get into resonance with our own selves, but since we are busy in the outer world, we use our shell which helps to communicate which is Maan- the mirror image of Atman. Most people in this world operate in the reverse direction as they communicate from Mann to Atman as I need Car, House, and Job as these all are liked by Mann and communicated to Atman with a belief system that this can make me happy while the happiest people on earth are those who communicate from inside to outside clearly telling the world- This is what I really require to be happy as this is my soul desire.

The [Book on Atmakarka](#) is the sole attempt, so anyone who reads it can understand the deeper meaning of their soul desire and be able to predict patterns and life choices based on Atmakarka as every work we do in this life and which becomes legendary is only due to one reason that we believed in it so much as it came out of our deep-rooted knowledge of Atman, which we were carrying from several lifetimes.

Coming back to Tithi – which governs our emotions, our feelings and the way we communicate from

Atman to Mann- what message are we carrying, how are we feeling in a day? What our Atman is trying to communicate as if you see Rahu Kaal- it is working in alternate groups and pair.

Morning Group **Evening Group**

Moon

Sun

Saturday Tuesday
Wednesday Friday
Thursday

Every day, based on which planet is ruling the day, there is a solar energy flare disturbance, and this flare disturbance happens, which blocks the communication of the Sun and Moon; it is a grahan happening at a minor level of 22.5 degrees. – This 90 mins is completely scientific as even the ISS- International space station, which is a man-made satellite is rotating at a speed of 90 mins/rotation as this is not by choice but by the necessity
Similarly, Rahu/Ketu, which are satellites of the Moon, blocks energy to Moon for 90 mins creating darkness in the absence of communication.

One thing you will notice during the dasa of Rahu or people who have prominent Rahu in their chart is the way these people speak; there is a lot of air movement and clarity in their speech, just like the language of snakes, a lot of hissing sounds, cleaning saliva which is coming out of the mouth from both ends as there is an absence of Atman, darkness comes in the head, and this can lead to all the wrong decisions, but this is also the time period which gives you time to connect to your own self and the realm of Rahu.

This is the best time to perform any remedies related to materialistic things. Solving problems of life, removing any chronic issues in life, and making offerings to ancestors this is the best time to it; one of the remedies you can try today is to offer Milk and honey for seven days regularly to the bottom of any tree. You can see the results of which will be your life will start to change for the better as suddenly events will happen which will be surprising for you.

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57 thoughts on “Science of Rahu Kaal”

SUMANGLA VEGAD

20 AUGUST 2023 AT 08:49

Wow, Sir this is an amazing article with a complete details about Rahu Kaal and also thanks for sharing the remedy too 😊🙏

Reply